

Total Quality Management Practices and its Implication to Teachers' Performance and School Success

Marvin M. Montenegro¹, Edilberto Z. Andal, Edd²

¹faculty of bukal elementary school, tiaong, quezon philippines

²dean of laguna state polytechnic university - san pablo city campus, philippines

ABSTRACT: the total quality management practices of school play an essential role in achieving school success in meeting its vision and mission. Hence, this study determined total quality management practices and its implication to teachers' performance and school success. It utilized quantitative and descriptive- correlational approaches to gather data. The respondents of this study were 156 public elementary teachers of tiaong i, district. It was conducted during the third quarter of the school year 2022-2023. It employed the used researcher-made questionnaire validated by educational experts in the research in data gathering procedures. The study revealed that there is a significant relationship between total quality management practices and school success. It is proposed that the school leaders should provide an avenue on providing teachers opportunities for their career growth and development as well as continuously involving them in the school relevant matters in decision-making resulting to boost their leadership and self-esteem. Then, continuous up skilling of instructional skills in terms of curriculum planning and assessing and reporting should be given priority to induce positive learning outcomes. Likewise, institutionalizing of total quality management practices is recommended in school to set clear standards of providing a relevant and quality educational services to the learners. Lastly, for the future researcher, a follow up study can be conducted using a regression analysis to identify other predictors and moderators about total quality management practices that promotes school success.

KEYWORDS: total quality management, teachers' performance, school success.

I. INTRODUCTION

A structured system that documents the processes, methods, and responsibilities for accomplishing quality policies and objectives is what is referred to as a quality management system (qms). A quality management system (qms) assists an organization in coordinating and directing its activities to better fulfill the needs of its customers and regulatory authorities, as well as to continuously enhance its level of effectiveness and efficiency. the most often used strategy for quality management systems is in accordance with iso 9001:2015, which is an international standard that outlines requirements for quality management systems.

The department of education (deped) of the philippines published its deped order no. 009, s. 2021 in february 2021. This document contained the guidelines for the institutionalization of a quality management system (qms) certifiable to iso 9001 standards. The goal of these guidelines was to ensure the consistent, effective, and efficient delivery of basic education services across all levels of governance, including the central office, regional offices, schools' division offices, and schools or community learning centers (clcs).

This order was issued in compliance with executive order no. 605, which was issued in 2007 and was titled institutionalizing the structure, mechanisms, and standards to implement the government quality management program (gqmp). The purpose of this order is to provide deped offices and schools or clcs with guidelines and standards to integrate deped internal systems and processes, upgrade people capacity, ensure capacity in the delivery of quality services, and foster continuous improvement that will result in enhanced and sustainably improved outcomes.

to attest the idea of tqm as the managing style of the curriculum leaders, birkinshaw & ansari (2015) remark that in education, the product are the learning achievements of each students as the main costumer; the services and process are the strategic managing styles and action that the school provide to its costumer; and the expectation are the learning and managing objectives that are set by the collaborating members of the institution such as the school head, teachers and parents and important stakeholders such as the barangay captain, government and non-government organization and other individual outside the school that play essential role in managing the school.

Total Quality Management Practices and its Implication to Teachers' Performance and School Success

According to bulger (2015), total quality management is directed by the top management, incorporates participation from all departments and individuals, and is a process that is ongoing. it requires leadership, ensuring the satisfaction of stakeholders, and accepting collective responsibility. According to an analysis of tqm quality concepts, the customer comes first and is one of the highest priorities. This indicates that the primary objective of this management style is to ensure the students' utmost welfare, regardless of whether the focus is on the students' cognitive, affective, or psychomotor development. To achieve quality, a company, school, or other organization or corporation must be motivated by the desire to provide the highest level of service to its clientele. when total quality management is included in the work ethics, it transforms into a way of life for the company, regardless of whether the job in question a component of an operation is or not.

The intention of the certification is for the betterment of the department and its stakeholders; however, it is also important to identify if everybody can go with the flow of the organization to better ensure that all the procedures are being followed. in the school setting total quality management practices involves leadership. Darling (1992), a complete quality management leader is defined as someone who inspires, through suitable ways, sufficient competence to persuade a group of persons to become willing followers in the attainment of corporate goals. reports study identifying the keys to successful leadership in quality management as focus with goal, significance via interpersonal interaction, confidence through position, and trust through appreciation.

in addition, according to nassor (2015), total quality management in terms of social environments and activities is one of the most useful operational strategies for enhancing a company's competitive advantage because it promotes, between other things, client involvement, satisfaction with work, employee training, employee-employer relations, and employee commitment. Total quality management is one of the best operational techniques for enhancing the competitiveness of an organization.

Furthermore, organizational success depends on effective communication since issues go unspoken and unaddressed in the absence of it. Therefore, successful communication occurs when the desired outcome comes from idea-sharing between multiple organizations when it is carried out in their chosen manner (malik, 2023).

meanwhile, rewards and recognition are considered as part of the tqm in which it is a manner of giving valuable things or other types of personal gratification to people or groups is referred to as rewarding them and continuing communication practice called recognition expresses gratitude for the contributions made by certain people or organizations. Even while reward is worthless without acknowledgment, recognition is a useful tool in and of itself. The following behaviors must be explicitly rewarded and acknowledged when an organization launches a tqm initiative: process improvement, cooperation and collaboration, problem prevention, customer happiness, and the manager's role as coach or facilitator. To ensure that rewards and recognition are aligned with the organization's operational goals, executives and hr officials should be involved (allen et.al, 2001).

Inasmuch, the physical condition of the school was also taken into account when ensuring that the tqm is practiced. A secure and active learning and development environment is essential, claims asiyai (2011). She upheld that such a setting is motivating and advantageous for training the intellect, heart, and hand in useful ways. Every student and adolescent deserve to learn in a setting that is respectful, positive, and safe. thus, factors such as acoustics, light, color, temperature, and seat arrangement in the school setting may be advantageous or disadvantageous to children' academic performance in classrooms. The three key factors that affect learning are noise, temperature, and seat arrangement. Furthermore, there isn't currently agreement on how particular physical characteristics of classrooms affect student learning outcomes. As a result, maintaining a physically secure school is essential (apter, 2014).

However, career support is also given weigh in the total quality management system, based on ilğan (2013), teachers need the support of school administrators in order to test out the most recent developments in their instructional strategies and include students in a variety of activities. Teachers' opinions may be influenced by how school administrators feel about professional development, as well as how much they respect it and how much they believe in it.

Nonetheless, teachers are considered as an important individual in the implementation of the tqm. Since they are the persons who educate young minds, their performance is also evaluated using a tool. In the philippine setting, ipcrf or individual performance commitment review form is utilized to ascertain the quality of teaching practices teachers explicit. such features that are assess in ipcrf includes the following: the first one is the content and pedagogy, egeberg et.al (2021) asserts that effective instruction necessitates an awareness of the students' perspectives on the material being taught. This is because teachers need to be aware of the past experiences, feelings, and learning preferences that students may bring to the classroom to effectively teach a subject.

In the same way, f. depaepe, l. verschaffel, and g. kelchtermans (2013) content knowledge, is the "what" of how students will learn. In other words, knowledge and subject-matter proficiency are the same. Pedagogy is the method used to help pupils acquire the abilities needed to show that they have understood the material.

Next, is the learning environment and diversity of the learners? shrestha et.al (2019), emphasized that one of the key factors influencing the success of a curriculum and, consequently, the academic accomplishment of students, is the learning environment.

Total Quality Management Practices and its Implication to Teachers' Performance and School Success

The quality of the curriculum, teaching and learning, and the development of student outcomes as practitioners are all impacted by the educational climate. By "the settings, external stimuli, and forces that challenge the individual and influence pupils' learning outcomes," bloom developed the educational or learning environment idea.

Moreover, curriculum and planning are another key essential role of the teachers. They are expected to craft and contextualized the learning experiences of the learners to make the learning more meaningful and relevant in their lives. alsubaie (2016), the process of creating a curriculum should be seen as one in which satisfying the needs of the learner fosters the student's learning. It cannot continue to be motionless. The curriculum must be a dynamic, living document that is always changing. It must be flexible enough to shift with societal and educational trends. Until then, it won't be able to effectively effect change in the educational process.

While assessing and reporting focused on the task of teachers to guarantee that they can monitor the progress of their students. According to harris (2015), assessments are essential when introducing an idea to a class. Both the pupils and the teachers gain from it. Assessments are a great tool to let students know how they are doing. Assessments are meant to point out pupils' errors and offer advice on how to fix them. Additionally, if pupils are having trouble remembering the subject, it helps them better reinforce it. It helps students express what they have learned and understand the material that the teacher has worked for weeks to prepare, develop, and teach. The outcomes of these tests, which are repeated throughout time, then assist in determining whether students have improved. It also promotes students' own motivation.

Nonetheless, another key determinant of total quality management is the satisfaction of the clientele based on the success that the school showcase in terms of facilities, educational services, and extra-curricular activities.

According to darmastuti, (2014) facilities and infrastructure are crucial to a school's performance, they are often used as a measure of the quality of instruction. The size of each institution's educational infrastructure and amenities has a substantial impact on how effectively students learn both inside and outside of the classroom.

While, the value of the educational service, student happiness, behavioral intentions, and referrals will all be impacted by the quality of the service, claim prentice et al. (2018). Hence, it is expected that the school provide variety of educational services suited to address the varied needs of the students. Lastly, according to tariq (2018), students who actively participate in extracurricular activities benefit in a variety of ways, including better exam results, academic performance, consistent attendance in class, and boosted self-confidence. The importance of striking a balance between extracurricular activities and academics cannot be overstated. While they aid students in gaining leadership and teamwork abilities, they should not take precedence over their studies. Students will benefit from this by developing their sense of self and self-worth, which will make them more trustworthy members of society.

given the scenario and determinants in total quality management systems the researcher, being in the service for five (5) years, has witnessed the changes that the iso brings in schools and he appreciates how the schools have become more organized and efficient in terms of its services and operational procedures. Thus, the main objective of the study is to determine the total quality management practices and its implication to teachers' performance and school success. specifically, it pursued to answer the following questions (1) the extent of practice of the total quality management in the school as perceived by the teacher-respondents with regards to leadership, social spaces and activities, communication, rewards and recognition, physical condition; and career support (2) level is the performance of the teacher be described in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning; and assessment and reporting (3) the satisfaction of the respondents towards schools total quality management practices in terms of school facilities, educational services; and extra-curricular activities (4) significant relationship between the extent of practice of the total quality management in the school and the school success.

Likewise, the study was also conducted in the anticipation that the schools, the administrators, the teachers, and personnel, and even the parents become aware on the vital role each of them plays in keeping the school upholding the total quality management system.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following data below contains various tables that present the results from the study's findings along with their interpretations. The data was analyzed and interpreted to draw conclusions and recommendations from the research.

Table 1: Total Quality Management Practices of School Heads

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Leadership	3.58	0.42	Highly Manifested
Social Spaces and Activities	3.56	0.44	Highly Manifested

Total Quality Management Practices and its Implication to Teachers' Performance and School Success

Communication.	3.61	0.45	Highly Manifested
Rewards and Recognition	3.60	0.47	Highly Manifested
Physical Condition	3.55	0.46	Highly Manifested
Career Support	3.66	0.53	Highly Manifested
Overall	3.59	0.46	Highly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.0 (highly manifested); 2.51-3.25 (moderately manifested); 1.76-2.50 (seldom observed); 1.0-1.75 (never manifested)

Table 1 illustrates the summary of tables of total quality management practices of school heads having an overall weighted mean of 3.59 with “highly manifested” as verbal interpretation. Indicator number 7 obtain the highest mean of 4.66 while indicator number 2 achieved the lowest mean of 3.56. It can be note that from the results that the respondent’s school heads practice total quality management in their designated school. They are aware on their duties and responsibilities to fully embrace the system of providing standardized services to the clientele in achieving their full potential development and embodied leadership that promotes quality services.

In support to the above results, bulger (2015), total quality management is directed by the top management, incorporates participation from all departments and individuals, and is a process that is ongoing. It requires leadership, ensuring the satisfaction of stakeholders, and accepting collective responsibility.

Table 2: level of teacher’s performance

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.57	0.51	<i>Highly Manifested</i>
Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	3.59	0.50	<i>Highly Manifested</i>
Curriculum and Learning	3.49	0.42	<i>Highly Manifested</i>
Assessing and Reporting	3.56	0.47	<i>Highly Manifested</i>
Overall	3.55	0.46	Highly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.0 (highly manifested); 2.51-3.25 (moderately manifested); 1.76-2.50 (seldom observed); 1.0-1.75 (never manifested)

Table 2 shows the summary of tables of level of teachers’ performance. It revealed that all four indicators are “highly manifested” by teachers with an average mean of 3.55. It can also be gleaned that learning environment and diversity of learners gained the highest mean of 3.59, while curriculum and learning got the lowest mean of 3.49. It reveals that the teachers should focus more on improving their performance in terms of curriculum and planning by crafting and designing lessons that is responsive to the needs, interest, learning styles and skills of their learners.

the table indicates also that the teachers have a strong sense of awareness in ensuring that their classroom is a safe place that signifies healthy learning environment with respect to the diversity of the learners while securing that they received the required skills to learn and able to track their progress through teachers’ assessment and reporting mechanisms.

Therefore, no matter what policies are set forth, it is the teacher's performance that has the greatest impact on the educational process because it is ultimately the teacher who must interpret and put these policies into practice through the teaching and learning process. The phrase does not just refer to how instruction is carried out or affects student accomplishment, personal development, or teacher traits. Instead, progress variables rather than product variables characterize teachers' performance.

Table 3: total quality management practices towards school success

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
School Facilities	3.45	0.45	<i>Highly Manifested</i>
Educational Services	3.59	0.42	<i>Highly Manifested</i>
Extra-Curricular Activities	3.58	0.43	<i>Highly Manifested</i>
Overall	3.54	0.43	Highly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.0 (highly manifested); 2.51-3.25 (moderately manifested); 1.76-2.50 (seldom observed); 1.0-1.75 (never manifested)

Table 3 illustrates the summary of tables regarding the total quality management practices towards school success. All three variables obtain “highly manifested” as verbal interpretation with an average mean of 3.54. It can be gleaned that the school implemented programs and practices which establishes the improvement of school facilities especially at present times when too much heat resulted to pupils’ discomfort thus limiting the number of hours of classes and shifting is utilized to solve the issue. However, despite of this the remediation and intervention program provided by the school is continuously implemented through blended learning. Nevertheless, extra-curricular activities are provided with strict adherence to the safety of the learners.

Total Quality Management Practices and its Implication to Teachers' Performance and School Success

To deduce as part of the organization's goals to achieve organizational excellence and superior customer satisfaction, tqm focuses on enhancing the efficiency of processes and responsiveness in meeting customer expectations. Achieving organizational excellence and excelling in customer satisfaction are among the organization's goals (ramlawati & putra, 2018)

Table 4: correlation between total quality management in the school and the school success

Total Quality Management	Teacher's Performance				School Success		
	CKP	LEDL	CP	AR	SF	ES	ECA
1.1. Leadership;	.354**	.360**	.413**	.328**	.458**	.563**	.534**
1.2. Social spaces and activities;	.353**	.386**	.416**	.360**	.528**	.608**	.576**
1.3. Communication;	.420**	.430**	.364**	.343**	.558**	.647**	.583**
1.4. Rewards and recognition;	.381**	.398**	.403**	.358**	.519**	.606**	.599**
1.5. Physical condition; and	.387**	.386**	.450**	.404**	.621**	.664**	.605**
1.6. Career support	.425**	.436**	.405**	.361**	.517**	.628**	.596**

Table 4 shows the correlation between the total quality management in the school and school success. it displays a significant relationship at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) among the variables. It is noteworthy that the school total quality management have positive impact in achieving school success because it set standards that must be followed to have a clear direction of what should be met.

moreover, total quality management practices of school leaders in terms of leadership, social spaces and activities, communication, rewards and recognition, physical conditions, and career support influence teachers' performance in such of the following ways: leadership of school heads influence teacher to set clear vision and attainable goals in improving the quality of their teaching practices to yield better learning outcomes, healthy working environment that is conducive to work is attain through well-maintained physical conditions of learning facilities, conducive spaces that promotes ease in doing activities and positive communication that is essential in planning and implementation of school paps (programs activities and projects). While career support and rewards and recognition motivate and inspires teachers to perform their job well as it stimulates them to advance in their career development.

Furthermore, total quality management practices are relevant to school success as to school facilities, educational services, and extracurricular activities as it serves as the basis in planning and implementing programs in relative to achieve better school performance. leadership, rewards and recognitions, career support set clear goals on what kind of educational activities are given priority in providing educational services both to students and teachers, the physical conditions and social spaces and activities are vital in improving the school facilities while communication is essential in extra-curricular activities so that the school, parents and stakeholders have a proper coordination on how things should be done resulting to attainment of shared visions and goals.

Numerous research also emphasized the importance of values such as total participation based on adequate education and training for the successful implementation of tqm or total quality management in various organizations. As a result, a quality management system includes teamwork, continuous improvement, a corporate quality culture, a customer focus, and a variety of management methods (fu et al. 2015; goh 2015; mosadeghrad 2015).

The findings of this study shown on the tables above, portrays the total quality management system that schools practice. It reveals that the schools can manifest the criteria that tqm set forth. The way school leaders drive the school in achieving the goals and objectives as to leadership, social spaces and activities, communication, rewards and recognition, physical conditions, and career support influence shows relevant impact in establishing a clear tqm that provides school a clear path to follow. Leadership, staff engagement, strategic planning, customer focus, and top management commitment were deemed to be the most crucial tqm practices. Successful tqm implementation is essential because it lowers defects and boosts internal quality, which meets client demands and expectations (svensson, m.et,al 2006, ismail 2015).

Furthermore, school leaders are expected to set directions in the implementation of the school total quality management system. Providing clear vision towards achieving goals incorporate with actions yields success. As asserts by ater top management commitment and leadership are a significant aspect in tqm implementation because they increase quality and performance by influencing other tqm practices. lawler (1992) and brown (2013) agreed also and state that successful tqm implementation requires complete participation and commitment from upper leadership, which is required for the formation of a culture of excellence which involves every individual in the organization.

Also, taking into accounts on the fundamental role that teacher plays in the tqm is manifested in the study. In here, using the ipcrf as tool to assess teachers' performance in delivering instructions provides a definite standard that is followed in assessing how well they are in doing their job in educating the students. Likewise, ensuring and guaranteeing quality services to the students through well-maintained facilities and program and activities offerings are squarely important aspects in tqm. According to kigozi(2019),tqm techniques classified under employee involvement include teamwork, human resources, stakeholder involvement, staff involvement, and participation from employees. It is also contended that employees gain new knowledge, a

Total Quality Management Practices and its Implication to Teachers' Performance and School Success

sense of accomplishment for achieving goals and objectives, and are inspired to work toward the organization's quality goals when they are involved in the day-to-day operations of the business, such as participating in decision-making and policy formulation (tari, 2011).

To deduce total quality management, reiterates a definite feature where the organization to follow. In the school context, it yields a clear foundation and framework that guides the school operation to follow the standards. It also set aspire the organization to continuously improve their services in their clientele. Providing services that meet client needs and expectations is the main goal of tqm adoption. Clients are a priority for organizations looking to enhance quality, based on notable theorists like deming (1986), juran (1995), and crosby (1979).

CONCLUSION

The findings in the study shows significant relationship between total quality management practices and school success. This implies that tqm practices that school leaders employed has a relationship with improving and evaluating teachers' performance as well as determining school success.

therefore, the following are the recommendations, it is proposed that the school leaders should provide an avenue on providing teachers opportunities for their career growth and development as well as continuously involving them in the school relevant matters in decision-making resulting to boost their leadership and self-esteem. Teachers are the persons who are the catalyst of change in the educational sector. Therefore, continuous upskilling of instructional skills in terms of curriculum planning and assessing and reporting should be given priority to induce positive learning outcomes. Institutionalizing of total quality management practices is recommended in school to set clear standards of providing a relevant and quality educational services to the learners. To the future researcher, a follow up study can be conducted using a regression analysis to identify other predictors and moderators about total quality management practices that promotes school success.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The researcher would like to convey his heartfelt appreciation to the following: laguna state polytechnic university – spc, for the high-quality education that helped him enhance knowledge for professional advancement and the approval to undertake this study. To montenegro family, who have overflowing support all throughout the whole duration of the masteral program.

REFERENCES

- 1) R. allen & r. kilmann (2001). the role of the reward system for a total quality management-based strategy. *journal of organizational change management - j organ change manage.* 14. 110-131. 10.1108/09534810110388036.
- 2) M. alsubaie curriculum development: teacher involvement in curriculum development. *journal of education and practice* (2002).
- 3) m. j. apter . towards a theory of things: reversal theory and design. *journal of motivation, emotion, and personality*, 2, 3-11. <https://doi.org/10.12689/jmep.2014.302>
- 4) R. asiyai. effective classroom management techniques for secondary schools. *african research review*, 5, 282-29, 2011.
- 5) J. a. ater . challenges facing the implementation of total quality management practices in public secondary schools in kenya." unpublished mba project. nairobi: kenyatta university 2013.
- 6) J. birkinshaw & s. ansari . understanding management models: going beyond "what and why" to "how" work gets done in organizations. 10.1093/2015
- 7) Brown (2013). "quality: where have we come from and what can we expect?" *the tqm journal*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 585–596 2013
- 8) p. b. crosby (1979). *quality is free: the art of making quality certain new york.* ny: mcgraw.1979
- 9) j.r. darling "total quality management: the key role of leadership strategies", *leadership & organization development journal*, vol. 13 no. 4, pp. 3-7. <https://doi.org/10.1108/0143773921001338> , 1992
- 10) A. darmastuti. local autonomy and inter-sector performance based governance inlampung province, indonesia. *journal of government and politics*,5(2), 169–175. doi:10.18196/jgp.2014.0016.
- 11) F. depaepe, l. verschaffel & g. kelchtermans . pedagogical content knowledge: a systematic review of the way in which the concept has pervaded mathematics educational research. *teaching and teacher education*, 34, 12–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2013.03.001>, 2013.
- 12) w. e. deming. "out of crisis, centre for advanced engineering study." massachusetts institute of technology, cambridge, 1986.
- 13) h.egeberg, a. mcconnney & a. price teachers' views on effective classroom management: a mixed- methods investigation in western australian high schools. *educ res policy prac* 20, 107–124 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10671-020-09270>
- 14) S.-l fu., s.-y. chou, c.-k. chen, & c.-w. wwang . assessment andcultivation of total quality management organisational culture—an empirical investigation. *total quality management & business excellence*, 26(1-2), 123-139. 2015.

Total Quality Management Practices and its Implication to Teachers' Performance and School Success

- 15) Harris. teacher leadership. international encyclopedia of the social & behavioral sciences: second edition, 24, 60–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-08-097086-8.92135-4>, 2015.
- 16) ilğan. effective professional development activities for teachers. uşak university journal of social sciences, special issue, 41-56, 2013.
- 17) S. ismail. “total quality management (tqm) practices and school climate amongst high, average and low performance secondary schools.” malaysian journal of learning and instruction, vol. 11, pp. 41–58, 2015.
- 18) j. m. juran (1995). "a history of managing for quality: the evolution, trends, and future directions of managing for quality" . asqc quality press milwaukee, 1995.
- 19) E. kigozi & on, j.. (2019). total quality management (tqm) practices applied in educations institutions: a systematic review of literature. international journal of innovative business strategies. 5. 341-352.10.20533/ijibs.2046.3626.2019.0045.
- 20) E. lawler."creating high performace organizations: survey of practices and results of employee involvement and tqm in fortune 1000 companies". wiley, 1995.
- 21) w.malik communication in quality management: understanding its importance and best practices, 2019.<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/communication-quality-management-understanding-its-best-ahmad-malik>,
- 22) s.mccombes descriptive research | definition, types, methods & examples. scribbr. retrieved may 24, 2023, from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>.
- 23) A.m. mosadeghrad. developing and validating a total quality management model for healthcare organizations, the tqm journal, 27 (5): 544 – 564, 2015.
- 24) f. m. nassor. the impacts of iso 9001 quality management system implementation on employees' performance of pension funds in tanzania: a case of national social security fund (nssf) (doctoral dissertation, the open university of tanzania, 2015.
- 25) G. prentice &j.brady & c. mclaughlin (2018). education service quality, value and satisfaction on student customer intentions and behaviour. dbs business review. 2. 10.22375/dbr.v2i0.27, 2018.
- 26) ramlawati, & a.h.p.k. putra (2018). total quality management as the key of the company to gain the competitiveness, performanceachievement and consumer satisfaction. international review of management and marketing, 8(5), 60-69, 2018.
- 27) Y. shrestha &, s. ben-menahem & g. krogh (2019). organizational decision-making structures in the age of artificial intelligence. california management review. 61. 000812561986225. 10.1177/0008125619862257, 2019.
- 28) M. svensson, and k. bengt. “tqm-based self-assessment in the education sector: experiences from a swedish upper secondary school project.” quality assurance in education, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 299–323, 2006